
ANALYSIS OF MAGNETIC ANOMALY OVER THE RIRUWAI YOUNGER GRANITE RING COMPLEX: A GEODYNAMIC IMPLICATION.

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The Riruwai Complex constitutes one of the Younger Granite Complexes in Nigeria within the Niger-Nigeria anorogenic belt province, located about 140Km south of Kano. It provides one of the finest examples of the complete cycle of anorogenicmagmaticactivities in Nigerian Province, and consists of alkaline volcanic and plutonic rocks ranging from pyroxene bearing porphyries, rhyolites and comendites, to riebeckite granites. The aeromagnetic intensity field anomaly of the Riruwai Younger Granite ring complex has been studied and analyzed to establish the tectonic nature of the complex and its influence on the geodynamics. The application of second derivative both in the x- and y-directions; (d^2U / dx^2) and (d^2U / dy^2) filters respectively, and Laplacian and polynomial regression analysis revealed a general NE-SW regional anomaly pattern within the Complex and along which the Riruwai Younger Granite is emplaced. Very low magnetic anomaly is associated with the biotite granites and the riebeckite bearing granites of the Complex. The very low anomaly is deemed to be attributed to highly evolved, late formed low density residual fluid rich magmatic material that were emplaced as granites as a separate magmatic phase, after an initial eruption of not so evolved volcanic phase. The general tectonic stress field traversing the Complex coincides with the NE-SW structural fabric within the Basement Complex of the region.

KEYWORDS: Riruwai Complex, Anorogenicmagmatism, Magnetic Anomaly, Tectonics, Geodynamics

INTRODUCTION

The Younger Granite petrographic province (Figure 1), exposed in Niger and Nigeria, consists in a north south belt of igneouscentres ranging in age from Ordovician (470 Ma) in northern Niger (Karche andVanchette 1976 ; Martin and Bowden, 1981) to Jurassic (144 Ma) in the most southerly complex in Nigeria. The ring structures and cupolas represent roots of volcanoes. The RiruwaiComplex provides one of the finest examples in the Nigerian province of the complete cycle of Younger Granite magmatic activity (Jacobson and Macleod 1977).The RiruwaiComplex with a distinctive topography is located 140 km south of Kano (Figure 2) and occupies an area of about 129 Km². Knowledge a priori show that the analyses of magnetic measurements yield significant and reliable information about subsurface geologic structures, even though essentially concealed (Dobrin and Savit, 1988;Bozzoet al., 1999;Blakely et al., 2000 and Nur, 2000; Ashano and Olasehinde, 2010). Analysis of aeromagnetic data from the Nigerian continental mass reveals magnetic lineations and regions of distinct magnetic character and field level which are interpreted as expressions of tectonic features related to igneous intrusives of various ages. The total field magnetic intensity data derives from the crystalline shield area with its characteristic Jurassic granitic ring complexes and neogenevolcanics, and the Benue Trough which is considered to be a failed-rift arm (Ajakaiyeet al., 1991). This work, on the basis of the above, employs the total magnetic data obtained over the Riruwai Younger Granite Ring Complex to establishthe tectonic nature of the complex and its influence on the geodynamics of the Complex. Total-field aeromagnetic anomaly data from the Riruwai Younger Granite Ring Complex (RYGRC) acquired by theNigerian Geological Survey Agency was used for the present study. The airborne Geophysical Survey (aeromagnetic) was flown and compiled by Hunting Geology and Geophysics Limited, and the map produced by the geological survey of Nigeria at a scale of 1:100,000 (GSN, 1975).

Figure 1. The Younger Granite Complexes showing the study area. Map modified after Macleod *et al.*(1971)

Figure 2. Location and the topography of the expression Riruwai Younger Granite Complex

GEOLOGY

The Ring Complex is emplaced into the Precambrian to early Paleozoic Basement Complex rocks. It is chemically distinct from the basement suites of cal-alkaline and sub-alkaline granitoid intruded at the close of the Pan –African Orogenicevent (Kinnard, 1984). Radioactive dating using Rb-Sr isotope of the complex, Van Breemen *et al* (1977) and Bonin (1988) show a relative 170 ± 5 ma age for the Complex. During the initial volcanic stages a considerable volume of acid lavas and associated pyroclastics was erupted, giving rise to a thick volcanic succession which also includes occasional flows of basalt. It is believed that the volcanism was accompanied by formation of large surface cauldron or caldera about 13km in diameter in which the bulk of the effusive volcanic material accumulated. The extrusive volcanic rocks are well preserved in north-western half of the complex while in the south-east and extreme north-west, the underlying vent structure can be seen. Towards the end of the volcanic cycle a large plug of quartz-fayalite-porphry was emplaced in the centre of the DutseShetu vent complex. During the plutonic cycle, the peripheral ring dyke of granite –porphyry, one of the

major structural feature of the complex, and the central granite plutons of biotite-and riebeckite-granite were emplaced beneath the volcanic pile (Jacobson and Macleod 1977).

METHODOLOGY: Magnetic Analysis

The total magnetic intensity data (Figure 3) of the Riruwai Complex draped on the geology was subjected to filtering in the second derivative both in x- and y-direction; (d^2U / dx^2) and (d^2U / dy^2) (Figure 4 and 5) respectively, and Laplacian (Figure 6) and polynomial regression (Figure 7) analysis to reveal the magnetic character of the complex as signals of different wavelength are isolated and hence enhanced anomalous features with a certain wavelength. Potential fields obey Laplace's equation, which states that the sum of the rate of changes of the field gradient in three orthogonal directions is zero(Kearey et al 2002). In normal Cartesian coordinate system with horizontal axes x, z, and vertical axis y, Laplace's equations is stated

$$\frac{d^2U}{dx^2} + \frac{d^2U}{dy^2} + \frac{d^2U}{dz^2} = 0 \quad \text{-----} \quad (1)$$

Where U refers to magnetic field and is a function of (x,y,z).

In the case of a two-dimensional field there is a no variation along the horizontal direction so that U is a function of x and y only and the equation becomes

$$\frac{d^2U}{dx^2} + \frac{d^2U}{dy^2} = 0 \quad \text{-----} \quad (2)$$

Separation of the variables gives solution to the partial differential equation

$$U_k(x,y) = (a \cos kx + b \sin kx)e^{ky} \quad \text{-----} \quad (3)$$

Where *a* and *b* are constants, the positive variable *k* is the spatial frequency or wave number, *U_k* is the potential field amplitude corresponding to that wavenumber and *y* is the level of observation. Equation (3) shows that a potential field can be represented in term of sine and cosine waves whose amplitude is controlled exponentially by level of observation.

Figure 3. Contoured total magnetic field intensity map over the Riruwai Younger Granite in gammas.

The application of Laplace calculates gradients both in x- and y-direction (second partial derivative) on the total magnetic intensity of the Riruwai Younger Granite Complex.

A plane surface was fitted to the data by polynomial regression analysis. This becomes necessary to remove the regional field. The expression for the regional field R(F) was:

$$R(F) = 7985 + 1.7120x - 2.803y \quad \text{-----} \quad (4)$$

Where x and y are unit spacing

This polynomial function produces the linear regional trends (Davies, 1973). These linear regional trends were applied to the aeromagnetic data from which the residuals were calculated. A profile A-B was taken to study the response of the total, derivatives and residual anomalies over the study area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tectonics and Geodynamics

Generally there is low magnetic anomaly associated with the biotite granites and the riebeckite bearing granites of the Complex (Figure 4-6). The profile AB was taken to study the response of the magnetism over the Riruwai Complex and compared with rock types over the same area (Figure 8 and 9). The profile reflects magnetic high and lows of anomalies which are response of deep seated structures. From the profiles negative anomalies from the Laplacian total derivative and the residuals are prominent on the contact between medium grained biotite granite and the fine grained biotite granite with values between -800 and -20 respectively (Figure 10). These anomalies could have been influenced by the presence of deep seated structures. The nature of magnetic anomalies near 4-6 km around the south, and near 10km around the centre within the biotite granite and the riebeckite bearing granites appear to be dominated by induced magnetization as low latitude bipolar magnetic anomaly with low towards north. The residual magnetic anomaly image (Figure 10) across the Complex reveals NE-SW trending anomalies which are the dominant magnetic features.

This trend reflects the Basement Pan African overprint induced by collision along the eastern edge of the West African Craton with an eastward dipping subduction zone, through which the Younger Granite intruded in a ENE-WSW and NE-SW linear pattern. (Rahamanet *al.*, 1984, Woakeset *al.*, 1987, Woakes 1989). These regional lineaments could be responsible for and the control of the Mesozoic uplift and intrusion anorogenic, alkaline Riruwai Younger Granite Ring Complex.

A geodynamic study of shield areas of Nigeria, (Scheidegger and Ajakaiye, 1985) and aeromagnetic anomalies and tectonic trend around the Benue trough (Ajakaiyeet *al.*, 1986) shows results of field studies, mainly of joint orientations, favoring the existence of a present-day sinistral shear in the Benue Trough which trend in the NE-SW direction and it also demonstrate the existence of narrow magnetic lineaments parallel to the margins of the Benue Trough, which can be matched with the oceanic fractures. Alkaline ring complexes which predate the opening of the Atlantic Ocean are concentrated along these lineaments, suggesting that they represent pre-existing zones of weakness in the African crust which may have influenced the rifting of the continental margins and the early development of Atlantic fracture zones (Ajakaiyeet *al.*, 1986).

Figure 4. d^2U/dy^2 filtered magnetic intensity map in the y direction of the Riruwai Younger Granite Ring Complex, showing the NE-SW trends within the Complex and Surrounding Basement.

Figure 5. d^2U/dx^2 filtered magnetic intensity map in the x- direction of the Riruwai Younger Granite Ring Complex.

Figure 6. (a)The Total derivative (Laplacian) magnetic intensity map draped onRiruwai Younger Granite Ring Complex.

Figure 7. Residual magnetic anomaly of the Riruwai Younger Granite Ring Complex showing trends in the NE-SW direction.

Figure 8. Profile A-B of the magnetic intensity, D^2U/dy^2 and D^2U/dx^2 respectively

Figure 9. Profile A-B of the total derivative, residual and the geology

As Alkaline granites derived from mantle magma represent less than 10% of the mass of basaltic parent magma, very efficient differentiation processes are active from the generation of the parent magma by upper mantle partial melting up to the final emplacement. While transport and storage of magma are likely to be triggered and enhanced by tectonic disturbance along shear and fault zones, their rate are essentially governed by buoyancy (Bonin, 1998; Ryan, 1992). The low density of ring complex materials relative to the upper crust is reflected by negative bouguer anomalies (Ajakaiye, 1970). Igneous activity occurred during three consecutive periods of 50 to 60 Ma; for each of these cycles, the igneous centres define an ENE trend (Bowden *et al.*, 1979). Relaxation of the internal magmatic pressure due to complete degassing of the liquid could be responsible for creation of set of tensile ring fractures, favouring underground cauldron subsidence below volcanoes. Martins and Bowden 1981, suggested that the peraluminous, biotite-bearing granites at Riruwai show disturbances, resulting from mild silification, ion exchange and incongruent dissolution of alkali feldspar. The most evolved residual liquid yield density grossly lowers than the wall rock and crystals (which also corresponds to the negative values for the Riruwai Younger Granite Ring Complex rocks shown in the data and results) favouring the in-situ accumulation of early formed crystal and trapping of late-stage liquids immediately below the roof chamber. Due to buoyancy, residual liquids can escape up to the surface level, propagated along the regional stress field in the NE-SW direction and the internal magmatic pressure. The emplacement of such highly evolved, late formed low density residual fluid rich magmatic materials as granites must have given rise to the biotite bearing and riebeckite bearing granites of the Riruwai Complex over which the lowest anomalies lie.

Figure 10. The geological boundaries draped on the image residual magnetism in the Riruwai Complex. Figure also shows direction of the dominant structural trend as negative values in the NE-SW direction.

1. Riebeckitemicrogranite
2. Kaffoalbite – riebeckite – granite
3. Fine grained biotite granite
4. Riebeckiteaegirine granite
5. Medium grained biotite granite
6. Kaffo river riebeckite granite porphyry
7. Pyroxene- fayalite-granite-porphyry
8. DutseShettu quartz-pyroxene-fayaliteporphyry
9. Basalt
10. Undifferentiated rhyolites, tuff, agglomerate and breccias
11. Early- rhyolite, breccias, commenditesand agglomerate
12. Crystalline Basement.

CONCLUSION

The second derivative both in x- and y-direction; (d^2U / dx^2) and (d^2U / dy^2) respectively, and Laplacian and polynomial regression analysis has been used in this study as tools for interpretation of the aeromagnetic data from the Riruwai Younger Granite Ring Complex. The 2-D profile reflects magnetic high and lows of anomalies which are response of deep seated structures. Negative anomalies from the Laplacian total derivative and the residuals are prominent on the medium grained biotite granite and the fine grained biotite granite with values between -800 and -20 respectively. The result from the analysis shows regional anomaly trends in the NE-SW

direction along which Riruwai Younger Granite Ring Complex. This could have propagated the emplacement of the complex in same direction inherited from the host Basement Complex.

REFERENCES

- Ajakaiye, D.E., (1970): Gravity investigation of Nigerian Younger Granite province. *Nature*, vol 225, pp 50-52.
- Ajakaiye, D.E., Hall, D.H., Millar T.W, Verheijen, P.J.T., Awad, M.B., and Ojo, S.B., (1986): Aeromagnetic anomalies and tectonic trends in around Benue Trough, Nigeria. *Nature* 319, pp582-584
- Ajakaiye, D.E., Hall, D.H., Ashiekaa, J.A., and Udensi, E.E (1991): Magnetic anomalies in the Nigerian continental mass based on aeromagnetic surveys. *Tectonophysics*, vol 192:1-2 pp211-230
- Ashano, E.C and Olasehinde, A. (2010): An Integrated study of the economic mineral potential of the Ropp Complex, North Central Nigeria. *Global Journ.Geol.Sci.* Vol. 8(1) pp1-15
- Blakely, R.J., Langenheim V.E., Ponce, D.A., and Dixon G.L (2000): Aeromagnetic survey of Amargosa desert, Nevada and California. A tool for understanding near surface geology and hydrology. *USGS Open file report* 00-188.
- Bozzo, E., Ferraccioci, F., Gambetta, M., caneva, G., Spano, M., Chiapini, M., and Davnoske, D., (1999): Recent progress in magnetic anomaly mapping over Victoria land (Antarctica) and GITARA5 survey. *Antarctic Science* 11(2) 209-216.
- Bonin, B. (1998): Alkaline rocks and Geodynamics. *Tr. J. of Earth Sciences* Vol 7.Pp 105-118
- Bowden, P., Bennett, I.N., Whitley, J.E. and Moyes, A.B. (1979): Rare earths in Nigerian Mesozoic granites and related rocks.in *Origin and Distribution of the Elements* (L.H' Ahrens, ed.). Pergamon, Oxford.
- Davies, C.J., (1973): statistical and data analysis in geology. *John Wiley and Sons, inc* New York. 550p.
- Dobrin, M.B and Savit, C.H., (1988): introduction to geophysical prospecting. 4th ed. *McGraw-Hill book company*, NY. 688p
- Draper, N., and Smith, H. (1981), Applied regression analysis, second edition, *Wiley- Interscience*, 709 pp.
- Jacobson, R.R.E. and Macleod, W.N (1977): Geology of Liruei, Banke and Adjacent Younger Granite ring-complex. *Geol. Surv. Nig. Bull.* 33. 117pp
- Karche J.P. & Vanchette, M. (1926): Migration des complexes subvolcaniques i structure annuelle du Niger. *Consequences. C.R. Acad. Sci. Paris* 282D, 2033-2036.
- Keary, P., Brook, M. and Hill, I. (2002): An Introduction to Geophysical Exploration. *Blackwell Science Ltd.* 262pp
- Kinnaird, J. A (1984): Hydrothermal alteration and mineralization of the alkaline anorogenic Ring complexes of Nigeria. *Journ. Afr. Earth Sci* 3:229-251.
- Martin, R.F and Bowden, P., (1981): Peraluminous Granite produced by rock fluid interaction in the Ririwai non-orogenic ring complex, Nigeria: Mineralogical evidence. *Canadian Mineralogist* Vol . 19, p.65-82
- Macleod, W.N., Turner, D.C. and Wright, E.P. (1971): The Geology of Jos Plateau. *Bull. Geol. Surv. Nigeria.* Vol30 No.1, pp 55-67
- Nur, A., (2000): Analysis of Aeromagnetic data over the Yola Arm of the Upper Benue Trough. *Journ. Min. and Geol.* Vol. 36(1) pp 77-84.

Rahaman, M.A., van Breeman, O., Bowden, P. and Bennett, J.N. (1984): Age migration of anorogenic ring complexes in Northern Nigeria. *Journ.of Geol.* Vol 92 p 173-184

Ryan, M.P., (1992): Neutral Bouyancy theory of magma transport and storage. Abstr.29 *int.Geol.Congr.*, Kyoto, 2-511.

Scheidegger,A.E and Ajakaiye,D.E (1985): Geodynamics of Nigerian shield area, *Journ. Afr Earth Sci* vol 3 issue 4 pp461-470

Van Breemen O, Pidgeon R.T, Bowden P (1977): Age and isotopic studies of some Pan-African granites from north central Nigeria. *Precambrian Res* 4:317-319.

Woakes, M., Rahaman, M.A., and Ajibade, A.C.,(1987): Some metallogenetic features of the Nigerian Basement. *Journ. Afri. Earth. Sci.* Vol 6.,No. 5. Pp655-664

Woakes, M. (1989): Mineral belts of Nigeria: a review. *Global tectonics and Metallogeny*, Vol.3, Nos.2 &3 pp 115-123.

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